

Measuring and Monitoring the Diversity of European Music Circulation with Open Source Technology and Data Sharing Within the Digital Music Observatory

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Daniel Antal, CFA, Reprex & University of Amsterdam
Andrés García Molina, PhD, Reprex

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Abstract

The *Feasibility study for the establishment of a European Music Observatory* (in short: EMO Feasibility Study)¹ has identified four critical data gaps related to the diversity and circulation of European music. This is a key business planning and policy problem, and of course, a serious shortcoming for better music research in Europe.

- The small and medium enterprise (SME)-dominated music ecosystem of labels, publishers, concert promoters, and tour managers have no clear understanding of the market opportunities in the Single market.
- Cultural policies that were relying on quota-based local content regulations and direct diversity targets in public broadcasting are powerless in a streaming dominated music scene.
- There are very few public data sources available for researchers and for educators.

The identified data gaps of the EMO Feasibility Study². This document has three parts:

I. Task list

1. Methodology Issues
- II. Filling the Data Gaps

1. Cross-border activity on radio stations
2. Cross-border activity on streaming platforms
3. Origins of songwriters behind the most popular songs—however, in our view, this should not be limited to the most popular songs!
4. Cross-border circulation of artists via live shows

II. The Diversity & Circulation Pillar of the Digital Music Observatory

1. From CEEMID to the Digital Music Observatory *This can be used in excellence / Objectives and WP Implementation.*
2. Cultural and Music Policy Relevance *This can be used as state-of the art in Objectives.*
3. Open Collaboration, Open Policy Analysis, and Open Data *This overlaps with our general WP Implementation.*

III. References

The goals of the Diversity and Circulation Pillar greatly overlap with some aspects of the Music Economy Pillar.

¹Feasibility study for the establishment of a European Music Observatory (European Commission et al. 2020).

²Feasibility study for the establishment of a European Music Observatory (European Commission et al. 2020, pp31–38).

Cultural diversity policy goals aim to ensure that the music scene of a country, region or city gets proper exposure on local media and stages; in addition, cultural diversity policy goals attempt to ensure less popular genres still find a way to their audiences. These objectives go hand in hand with some competition policy and consumer protection targets, and they also align well with the objectives of intellectual property and copyright policies. Because almost all income of artists is connected to the use of music, a lack of diversity, and less opportunities for small-language repertoires and genres (such as classical or jazz music), also lead to inadequate income connected to their composers, performers, and a devaluation of their copyrights and neighboring rights. An excessive concentration of volume of use, and therefore revenues and market share for certain nations, or large publishers and labels conflicts with competition policy goals.

The 8 years of research and policy use history of the Digital Music Observatory (formerly CEEMID) is connected both to competition law-based cases and cultural policy use cases, using the same data, and an overlapping methodology.

In the 21st century, about 60% of the recorded music sales are made by streaming and user-uploaded content platforms where it is mainly not human curators but AI algorithms that match the vast supply of content to users. These AI algorithms use machine learning from the available biographical, musicological, natural language processed lyrics and review information, the artists' music history and their user interaction history, user demographics, and other complex, interrelated information. Our experience shows that a strong presence on global streaming and UUC streaming (User-Uploaded Content, like YouTube's platform) platforms requires a very sophisticated data infrastructure and data knowledge that is not present in smaller, independent music businesses, and not even in small-country national organizations.

The data of the Digital Music Observatory is used—outside the scope of this proposal—in trustworthy AI research³ where we try to assign blame for the less-than-optimal outcome for small business and small country repertoires for copyright data and metadata problems. These problems are related to a larger problem that we work in both **Economics of Music** and the **Music Diversity and Circulation Pillars**. Indirectly, because copyright data management/metadata management problems are among the causes of *Music export, Structure of the market, Value of EU's music sector, Employment, Independent music, Neighbouring rights* problems and data gaps of the *Economy of Music Pillar*, not only that of the Diversity & Circulation problems. Indirectly, because researching these problems requires the same data sources, the same data processing about music present in broadcast, retransmission, streaming and other non-mechanical channels of distribution.

In other words, the *Economy of Music Pillar*⁴ relies on very similar data like the *Diversity and Circulation Pillar*⁵, but it uses the data in different analytical models.

Please find the authoritative copy of this document (or later versions) on Zenodo. Subjects: Cultural diversity policies; Music industry Recommender systems (Information filtering)

Proposed Work in the Diversity & Circulation Pillar of the Digital Music Observatory

Task list

This is a part of our Proposal for the Towards a competitive, fair and sustainable European music ecosystem⁶ grant call.

Our aim is to fill the identified data gaps of all four areas in the *EMO Feasibility Study*, i.e. Cross-border activity on radio stations, Cross-border activity on streaming platforms, Origins of songwriters behind the most popular songs—and, Cross-border circulation of artists via live shows. It is important to note that the latter will overlap with T1.1.1, as this is an important issue in music exports, too.

³Trustworthy Autonomous Systems Hub: Eight new TAS projects announced, Trustworthy Autonomous Recommender Systems on Music Streaming Platforms

⁴Observing, Monitoring and Analysing the Economy of Music in Europe with the Digital Music Observatory (Antal and Molina 2022a).

⁵Measuring and Monitoring the Diversity Circulation of European Music with Open Source Technology and Data Sharing Within the Digital Music Observatory (Antal and Molina 2022b).

⁶Research and innovation on cultural heritage and CCIs - 2022 (HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01)

Methodology Issues

According to the *EMO Feasibility Study*, “There are already some potential sources to start tracking and monitoring the circulation of European repertoire . . . most data suppliers do not identify artists by nationality. Some data supplier’s associate recordings with International Standard Recording Codes (ISRC), but it does not necessarily contain data on the country of origin of the artists. [...] Identifying songs by their language could also prove to be problematic, since this is not usually provided by data suppliers and would require manual inputting.”

The Towards a competitive, fair and sustainable European music ecosystem⁷ grant call stresses out that “proposals should also elaborate on lacking definitions related to national and European repertoire.”

Drawing on the methodology of modern ethnomusicology, we will show that national and European repertoire definitions should not be binary, but follow a continuum between non-European and European, or, as we have explored in our *Listen Local Study*, between non-Slovak and Slovak. This means that the definition of Slovak (or European) will be more connected to a Slovak/European performer or Slovak/European composer – and implicitly, to a Slovak/European producer – because identifying Slovak/European languages in lyrics, and particularly the ‘musical language’ of Slovak/European genres is not possible in a binary manner. Therefore, not only the observation and measurement problems of the

1. Cross-border activity on radio stations
2. Cross-border activity on streaming platforms overlap with
3. Origins of songwriters behind the most popular songs, but also with *Music export, Structure of the market*, and the *Value of EU’s music sector* in the **Economy of Music Pillar**.

In the *Feasibility Study On Promoting Slovak Music In Slovakia Abroad*, we have developed a method to make this process far more effective, combining a highly automated write-in process, that uses natural language processing, copyright management data, and other available (and public) data sources with very limited curatorial oversight perfected by a musicologist with rights management experience at SOZA, Dominika Semaňáková, who remains a curator of the Digital Music Observatory. We combined this with an opt-in process, where a rights management organization (in our example, SOZA), but any rights management organization, like a digital distributor, and independent rights management company, a collective management organization, or even a larger label or publisher, possessing a GDPR compliant database can ask its members or represented artists to opt-in to the database with personal data.⁸ Our system relies on fully open-source code elements, which we will further develop in under the **Innovation Pillar**. Currently, one of its key components, the *spotifyr* package, which is a very extensive wrapper around the Spotify Rest API is released on the peer-reviewed CRAN software archive and it is regularly maintained by Reprex’s team⁹. Our aim is to place the data derived for these purposes into databases that have a full interoperability with important data sources of the music industry, such as the MusicBrainz open-source database, or Wikipedia.

Most music is sold by autonomous systems, i.e., AI algorithms. Algorithms learn from categorization and features. Our categorization for the Slovak Demo Music Database was inspired by Reprex’s co-founders earlier work in ethnomusicology that connects qualitative and quantitative data, particularly in the way music is categorized and used through various forms of labour¹⁰. The question of categorizing music is anything but trivial; arguably, the discipline of ethnomusicology has grappled with that very challenge from its inception, as the prefix “ethno-” was first appended as a way to differentiate between the musicologies and their purported objects of study: “Western” music and the music of the rest of the world. The complexity of understanding musical categories—be they based on genre, nationality, medium, or use, among others—has never gone away; the logics behind ways of categorizing music remain contentious, especially in the context of digital streaming¹¹. Our approach blends a grounding in ethnomusicological sensibility with a practical understanding of the relatively limited universe of categories applied to music in order to avoid strict or binary definitions (e.g. “Slovak” versus “not Slovak”), instead favoring a fuzzy approach that can be engineered into features used in algorithms.

According to the *EMO Feasibility Study*, “creating reliable tools to monitor what kind of repertoire circulates on digital platforms or via radio will require access to vast amounts of data from Digital Service providers (DSPs) or third-party aggregators.” Our approach that has been piloted in the Central

⁷Research and innovation on cultural heritage and CCIs - 2022 (HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01)

⁸See the Annex of the *Feasibility Study On Promoting Slovak Music In Slovakia & Abroad* (Antal 2020b, p34–37).

⁹*spotifyr*: R Wrapper for the Spotify Web API (Thompson et al. 2021)

¹⁰Molina (2020)

¹¹See for example Liz Pelly: *Streambait Pop* (Pelly 2018).

European Music Industry Report and the UK Intellectual Property Office’s Music Creators’ Earnings project shows that there is much easier, cheaper and more reliable way that requires advanced computer science, statistics know-how usually present in quantitative finance research¹².

It is both theoretically, practically, and legally possible to analyse diversity, circulation, export, and valuation information with well-designed, anonymous samples or with the creation of synthetic datasets that contain random data which follows the statistical properties of the true data (Osimo et al. 2019; Senftleben et al. 2021; Antal 2020a). There are advanced statistical techniques that can make the rich information available in these hidden datasets for the benefit of the entire industry and for evidence-based policy design.

CHART 2: THE DEGREES OF DATA SHARING (adapted from OECD and Open Data Institute)

CEEMID in 2020 has released a synthetic data product, the CEEMID-CI streaming volume and price indexes, which were based on a dataset containing about 300 million royalty statements. Inspired by the stock exchange and bond market indexes that make fast-changing and hard to comprehend information available for market participants in a simple, timely, and easy-to-understand manner, CEEMID created streaming indexes for 5 years and 20 European countries. Instead of showing aggregate national revenue growth (that is mainly driven by the growth of the 1% most successful artist, and often affected by exchange rate changes, minimum licensing agreements, and other factors), the CEEMID-CI indexes showed the achievable typical streaming volumes, and the price of a typical stream in various platforms (Spotify, Apple, Deezer, YouTube). The indexes, presented in the *Central European Music Industry Report*, were seen as a best practice by the European Commission’s and Geoth Institute’s CreativeFlip project, and the indexes were further used in policy projects initiated in the United Kingdom¹³.

¹²See particularly Chapter 4.2 of the Central European Music Industry Report (Antal 2020a), the Music creators’ earnings in the digital era and the supporting document An Empirical Analysis of Music Streaming Revenues and Their Distribution (Antal 2021), and the dynamic research document of submitted for the inquiry of the UK Competition Market Authority (Antal 2022a). The datasets and documents are available in the Digital Music Observatory, and with authoritative copies in our dedicated space on the European open science repository Zenodo, and they are indexed by the European network of open access repositories OpenAIRE).

¹³The Central European Music Industry report and its data is available online in many formats (Antal 2020a), and the calculations created for the *Music Creators’ Earnings in the Digital Era* project of the UK Intellectual Property Office can be found in our Digital Music Observatory.

Total Streams* of Median (Typical) Song

*Apple Music + Deezer + Spotify, rolling monthly sums of three month
Source: Central European Music Repot by CEEMID & state51 © 2019

One of our main methodological goals is to improve the selection method to the so-called ‘basket’ of songs, created in methodologically-similar ways to a basket of stocks or bonds with financial market indexes. A well-known financial market indicator, the Dow Jones Industrial Average, for example, is a specially-weighted average price of 30 stocks. While it does not contain the price of any single company out of the 30 stocks in its basket, it is an easy-to-understand indicator of price and economic return that represents a large market segment of securities. Many companies that were in the ‘basket’ in 1896, when the DJIA was first calculated, do not exist anymore, but a well-designed algorithm to replace stocks in the basket have ensured that it remains a widely-used anchor even 127 years after its inception. Our goal is to design a similar selection method that will select representative works/recordings, or “songs,” from the Slovak, Swedish, or other national repertoires, and which will allow us to represent the volume, price, and return movements to be observed with access to about 30-50 recordings’ data per geographical, genre, or artist maturity segment (e.g., “Italian songs,” “Emerging artists,” “World Music.”)

When we work with streaming data, we have two methodological problems. First, nobody has access to the full list of copyright-protected works/recordings because copyrights and neighboring rights, unlike patents, do not have a global database. Second, the vast majority of “songs” are not played in any given royalty payment period (which is monthly with accruals on streaming platforms and usually annually on broadcasting and retransmission platforms.) Because the average income and play count is close to zero, and the median value is zero in all large portfolios of “songs,” we must use some dynamic, reverse sampling to understand the part of the global, national, or genre-repertoire that is used at all. This problem is often present in quantitative finance in the context of two problems: understanding financial risk in the long-tail (in Monte Carlo simulation, for example), and representing the price movements, sales volumes, and return of illiquid, infrequently-traded securities.

State of the art

Pillar 2 - Circulation & Diversity					
pillar	Topic	problem	availability	Description	feasibility
Pillar 2	Streaming activity	- volumes	Data gap	Due to the huge volumes of streaming data and the difficulties of accessing this data, monitoring streaming activity could be a challenge. However, the recent announcement by elsen that they are now providing a global streaming chart, but also national streaming charts, should provide EMO with a potential tool to monitor this activity.	
Pillar 2	Live music cross-border activity		Data gap	At this stage there are no pan-European tools that allow for analysis of the cross-border activity of European artists. Listings from Liveurope, ETEP and other exchange programmes will be a good place to start, but these are far from geographically comprehensive and it will be necessary to build a tool to monitor the circulation of European artists.	
Pillar 2	Streaming activity	- prices	Data gap	Due to the huge volumes of streaming data and the difficulties of accessing this data, monitoring streaming activity could be a challenge. However, the recent announcement by elsen that they are now providing a global streaming chart, but also national streaming charts, should provide EMO with a potential tool to monitor this activity.	
Pillar 2	Streaming activity	- exports	Data gap	Due to the huge volumes of streaming data and the difficulties of accessing this data, monitoring streaming activity could be a challenge. However, the recent announcement by elsen that they are now providing a global streaming chart, but also national streaming charts, should provide EMO with a potential tool to monitor this activity.	
Pillar 2	Live music cross-border audiences		Data gap	At this stage there are no pan-European tools that allow for analysis of the cross-border activity of European artists. Listings from Liveurope, ETEP and other exchange programmes will be a good place to start, but these are far from geographically comprehensive and it will be necessary to build a tool to monitor the circulation of European artists.	
Pillar 2	Live music cross-border revenues		Data gap	At this stage there are no pan-European tools that allow for analysis of the cross-border activity of European artists. Listings from Liveurope, ETEP and other exchange programmes will be a good place to start, but these are far from geographically comprehensive and it will be necessary to build a tool to monitor the circulation of European artists.	

Cultural and Music Policy Relevance

Until the 1990, most radio and television broadcasting was state-owned and maintaining an audience for local music was internalized in these institutions that were seen as important tools of national cultural policies in most European countries. With the increasing plurality of radio and television, more and more countries introduced local content regulations to secure enough airtime for their national, regional or city artists. In our *Feasibility Study On Promoting Slovak Music In Slovakia & Abroad* (in short: Listen Local Study) we have surveyed more extensively such approaches, and it is our goal to systematically review such regulations and policies¹⁴.

Promoting national or locally relevant music has several policy measures, but broadcasting quotas are particularly interesting for our subject. Regulations aiming for cultural diversity, particularly in music, usually take the form of *local content regulations*, because it is not particular composers or performers, but instead recorded fixations or audiovisual content that embed (“synchronizes”) music as *content* to be regulated. From an evidence-based policy perspective, we believe that the data gaps to be filled should particularly aim for monitoring such regulations and creating impact assessments for them.

For example, in France, the *Loi du 1er février 1994* requires that 40% of music broadcast during peak hours be **French-language titles, half of which are required to come from new artists or to be new productions** since 1996. The conditions were modified in 2000, affording stations with different listener demographics different quotas. In recent years, the French national assembly discussed various modification possibilities. In 2016, a bill was introduced to *increase* the French-language requirement, which was heavily criticized by both radio stations and artists, and in 2019, a parliamentary report suggested genre-specific quotas (Reynaud 2016; 20 Minutes 2019), similarly to Australia and some other countries, because certain genre-based stations (e.g., rock and electro) could hardly fill their quotas.

Most of the music and film consumption in the 21st century is mainly based on recommendation systems. Recommendation systems are machine learning applications that provide information to users about content they may like. In the 20th century this role was mainly played by radio editors. In the 21st century algorithms take over this role directly or indirectly: currently, radio editors and festival and concert promoters increasingly use algorithms in their work. A key difference between broadcasting and streaming music is that in the broadcast stream every user sees or hears the same content. In digital streaming, each user sees a different movie or listens to a different song or radio program. Broadcasters were modelling large demographic groups for their content selection, while streaming providers are exploiting personal information for each subscriber.

Spotify’s recommendation system (Jacobson et al. 2016) is a mix of content- and collaborative filtering that exploits information about users’ past behaviour (e.g. liked, skipped, and re-listened songs), the behaviour of similar users, as well as data collected from the users’ social media and other online activities, or from blogs. Deezer uses a similar system that is boosted by the acquisition of Last.fm – big data created from user comments are used to understand the mood of the songs, for example.

YouTube, which plays an even larger role in music discovery, uses a system comprised of two neural networks: one for candidate generation and one for ranking. The candidate generation deep neural network provides works on the basis of collaborative filtering, while the ranking system is based on content-based filtering and a form of utility ranking that takes into consideration the user’s languages, for example. (Covington, Adams, and Sargin 2016)

You can find and re-use all our charts, like our data, separately, or in reports¹⁶.

Most of the music and film consumption in the 21st century is mainly based on recommendation systems. Recommendation systems are machine learning applications that provide information to users about content they may like. In the 20th century this role was mainly played by radio editors. In the 21st century algorithms take over this role directly or indirectly: currently radio editors, festival and concert promoters are increasingly using algorithms in their work. Music recommendation systems—at least at the time of analyzing these data gaps—are not subject to content regulation in Europe. However, they are increasingly subject to trustworthy AI polices and to some extent, copyright regulation (regulating

¹⁴Feasibility Study On Promoting Slovak Music In Slovakia & Abroad, Slovak version: *Projektová štúdiá propagácie slovenskej hudby na Slovensku a v zahraničí* (Antal 2020b, 2020c).¹⁵, with some additions and follow up on some markets.

¹⁶See for example, *A potential goal-based recommendation system that promotes the national music repertoire on various music distribution and broadcasting platforms* in our visualization collection in the Figshare repository (Antal 2022b). The data and reports can be found on in the in the Digital Music Observatory collection of the Zenodo open science repository.

Figure 1: Goal setting

data interoperability.) The relevant methodologies, data standardization and datasets of the Digital Music Observatory are currently being used in trustworthy AI contexts (understanding potentially harmful biases of autonomous music recommendation systems in music.) However, in the future, we would like to provide empirical underpinning general copyright data management and metadata management problems, too, following the research program of the Digital Music Observatory, IViR, and Reprex (Senftleben et al. 2021).

In the area of live music, the freedoms of the European Union and the Single market have created increasing opportunities for performers to increase their audience beyond their national borders. Yet, touring in Europe is not without obstacles. Musicians generally do not have an employer, and they receive payment for each concert. For instance, this might mean that a Pan-European tour may have tax and social security consequences in many countries.

Cross-border activity on streaming platforms

According to the *EMO Feasibility Data* “due to the huge volumes of streaming data and the difficulties of accessing this data, monitoring streaming activity could be a challenge. However, the recent announcement by Nielsen that they are now providing a global streaming chart, but also national streaming charts, should provide EMO with a potential tool to monitor this activity.”

However, our experience in United Kingdom, Slovakia, and Czechia shows that this approach is not viable. The Music Creators’ Earnings in the Digital Era policy document of the UK Intellectual Property Office shows that that “the top 0.1% most popular tracks achieved more than 40 per cent of all streams in all years (based on October) and the top 0.4 per cent of tracks accounted for more than 65% of all streams from 2016 onwards. The top 1 per cent of tracks account for between 75 and 80% and the top 10 per cent for between 95 and 97%, in all years from 2016 to 2020.” This means 99% of the artists never get to the top 1%, which is still far from the charts.

The alternative approach piloted by Reprex and the Digital Music Observatory with the CEEMID-CI streaming indexes shows that the application of advanced computer science, dynamic portfolio optimization techniques from quantitative finance, and advanced statistics can lead to a more feasible and more representative approach. It is theoretically, practically, and legally possible to analyse diversity, circulation, export, and valuation information with well-designed, anonymous samples, or with the creation of synthetic datasets that we will create similar to stock market indexes, following or successful, 20-country demonstration for the period of 2015-2019 in the Central European Music Industry Report and the Music Creators Earnings’ in the Digital Era project.¹⁷

¹⁷See particularly Chapter 4.2 of the Central European Music Industry Report (Antal 2020a), the Music creators’ earnings in the digital era (Hesmondhalgh et al. 2021, p199, p28) and the supporting document An Empirical Analysis of Music Streaming Revenues and Their Distribution (Antal 2021), and the dynamic research document of submitted for the inquiry of the UK Competition Market Authority (Antal 2022a). The datasets and documents are available in the Digital Music Observatory, and with authoritative copies in our dedicated space on the European open science repository Zenodo, and they are indexed by the European network of open access repositories OpenAIRE).

Our approach does not focus on the less than 0.9% of the artists who ever make it to the charts, but on the typical artist. In our demonstration for the period 2015-2019, we created volume and price indexes for a ‘typical’ and ‘successful’ artist in 20 countries.

Our approach is to create a better representation of artists and labels for all EU countries.

Cross-border activity on radio stations

As the Policy Brief *A Symphony, not a Solo*, has shown, for example collective management organizations [CMOs] “do not own *superstar datasets* and their existing data coverage is shrinking. One of the common mistakes in the data economy is that organizations and people—and CMOs are no exception—tend to overestimate the value of their data. Holding on to their data will not provide the sustainable competitive advantage they need to survive. And monetizing those data is difficult because of the lack of granularity. The solution is to move towards greater data openness and sharing. It’s not just about opening up data held by CMOs, but to favor greater data sharing across the industry value chain.” (Osimo et al. 2019)

According to the *EMO Feasibility Study* “Through local societies and GESAC and CISAC, it is possible to draw a picture of the sector on a national and pan-European level. However, the flow of rights that circulate between the various countries through authors’ societies’ reciprocal agreements is not available and could constitute a good indicator of the circulation of repertoire, in line with the Transparency report requested by the Directive 2014/26/EU on collective management of copyright and related rights, which requires to provide information on relationships with other collective management organisations, with a description of at least the following items: amounts received from other collective management organisations and amounts paid to other collective management organisations, with a breakdown per category of rights, per type of use and per organisation.”¹⁸

There are several potential data sources available for this problem. On an aggregated level, the CISAC Financial Database has this information on a standardized level for every European country—in fact, globally. This database is not public, but it is available for every CISAC member, including members of our Consortium.

Origins of songwriters behind the most popular songs

The *EMO Feasibility Study* describes this data gap as the **Origins of songwriters behind the most popular songs**, but we think that the problem is much broader. “[...] *Another important factor to rely on in order to determine the circulation of repertoire would be through the identification of the country of the repertoire owner (for example, Selah Sue is an artist from Belgium but the repertoire owner is a French label). Identifying songs by their language could also prove to be problematic, since this is not usually provided by data suppliers, and would require manual inputting.*”¹⁹

In the *Feasibility Study On Promoting Slovak Music In Slovakia Abroad*, we have developed a method to make this process far more effective, combining a highly automated write-in process²⁰.

In our view, however, the *EMO Feasibility Study* underestimates the problem of the definition of the ‘nationality’ of music, composers, or performers. “The definition of Slovak content is often connected to a Slovak performer or Slovak composer—and implicitly, to Slovak producer—because identifying Slovak music genres from a musicological point of view, or Slovak lyrics from a language use point of view is difficult to measure and enforce.”²¹

Our research in Slovakia made it clear that generally, various income and export goals in an economic sense are not met exactly partly due to the same reasons for which cultural diversity is diminishing on streaming platforms. As the research of IViR, Reprex, and some of our partners points out, often the expected (present value) income of music works and recordings is smaller than the cost of documenting them to the ever-increasing standards set by copyright management systems and streaming or UUG platforms. Because these platforms mainly use autonomous systems to deliver music to the final audience, they use a large variety of musicological, biographical, review, user interaction history, and other information to keep works/recordings in circulation. Such data is often missing or lacks a sufficient quality when

¹⁸ *EMO Feasibility Study* (European Commission et al. 2020, pp31–34).

¹⁹ Feasibility study for the establishment of a European Music Observatory (European Commission et al. 2020, pp31–34).

²⁰ See the Annex of the *Feasibility Study On Promoting Slovak Music In Slovakia & Abroad* (Antal 2020b, p34–37).

²¹ Feasibility Study On Promoting Slovak Music In Slovakia & Abroad (Antal 2020b, p18.).

produced by self-published artists and small labels that do not have an independent data/IT department, or where most of the information is not available in the English language.

Research into this problem suggests that overcoming the cold-start problem can be best done with a combination of bringing in more information about both *the artist* and the *music recording* itself. This is hardly surprising: while recommendation engines are, for practical reasons, mainly artist recommendation systems, providing an accurate description of lesser-known artists and their music helps to better place artists on and their music helps to better place the artist on recommendation lists (Oramas et al. 2017).

Cross-border circulation of artists via live shows

The Digital Music Observatory/CEEMID has been piloting various cross-border circulation data collection methods in the past years. Our music professional surveys collected information about the budgets, audience sizes, and even the destinations of foreign performances. We have also reviewed the data availability at CISAC/GESAC member societies²².

The Diversity & Circulation Pillar of the Digital Music Observatory

According to the *EMO Feasibility Study*, "there is already an existing pool of data that would allow the European Music Observatory to start compiling information about the European music sector. Various potential sources and providers of data are ... [*available, such as our Digital Music Observatory*]. Many of these providers have already indicated support for a future European Music Observatory, and are willing to collaborate and provide data. However, some data is not collected or is not aggregated in a way that it can be compared across Europe²³.

From CEEMID to the Digital Music Observatory

The Digital Music Observatory (formerly CEEMID) has been identified among these data sources²⁴. CEEMID was originally an acronym for a data integration project that aimed to *Create a Regional Music Database to Support Professional National Reporting, Economic Valuation and a Regional Music Study*²⁵. According to the European Commission's feasibility study, "CEEMID can transfer thousands of indicators that are reproducible and verifiable, open-source software that creates them to a European Music Observatory. In particular, CEEMID provides a useful and interesting approach to harnessing the possibilities of open data in Europe in relation to the music sector, which should be further explored by the European Music Observatory in its start-up phase."²⁶

The Digital Music Observatory is built on the gradual, and open extension of the original CEEMID consortium, and builds on practical research and innovation that contributed to many music policy goals in an increasing number of countries since 2014. The original CEEMID consortium delivered the first Hungarian music industry studies (followed by several subsequent ones), the Slovak national music industry study, *Private Copying in Croatia*, and eventually the regional Central European Music Industry Report.²⁷ All of these industry studies addressed the problem of shrinking competitiveness in of the small language repertoire in the streaming era.

The Feasibility Study is built on the consensus of many European music organizations around a shared understanding "that a European Music Observatory should act as a centralised music data and an intelligence hub at European level." However, as a pilot project and policy brief carried out in Finland²⁸,

²²This topic was also touched in our national music industry reports and the Central European Music Industry Report.

²³Feasibility study for the establishment of a European Music Observatory (European Commission et al. 2020, pp31–34).

²⁴Our observatory is mentioned to be able to participate with "data collection and integration system based on open data, opensources and online surveys" in all pillars of the future European Music Observatory, including Diversity & Circulation (European Commission et al. 2020, p40.)

²⁵The original aim of CEEMID was *Measuring and Reporting Regional Economic Value Added, National Income and Employment by the Music Industry in a Creative Industries Perspective* Three national collective management societies and their consultant signed Memorandum of Understanding about this in 2014 (Artisjus et al. 2014).

²⁶Feasibility study for the establishment of a European Music Observatory (European Commission et al. 2020, pp147–148).

²⁷A ProArt zeneipari jelentése (Antal 2015) and *The Growth of the Hungarian Popular Music Repertoire: Who Creates It And How Does It Find An Audience* (Antal 2017); *Správa o slovenskom hudobnom priemysle* (Antal 2019b), *Private copying in Croatia* (Antal 2019a), Central European Music Industry Report (Antal 2020a).

²⁸See the Policy Brief *A Symphony, not a Solo* (Osimo et al. 2019).

or the CEEMID project in Central and Eastern Europe has shown, has its limits. We believe that the existing data availability is better than that described in the *Feasibility study*, and since the creation of this report, it has only got better.

Since 2014, the Digital Music Observatory (former CEEMID) successfully piloted data collection, standardization and harmonization procedures that can fill all the data gaps identified in the music diversity and circulation pillar of the future European Music Observatory. CEEMID was transformed into a “Demo Music Observatory” on 15 September 2020²⁹ and eventually named *Digital Music Observatory* in 2021. Its policy relevance was also recognized in the United Kingdom after Brexit³⁰.

The Digital Music Observatory follows the *Open Policy Analysis Guidelines*³¹ The OPA Guidelines give practical guidance on how to improve the transparency, replicability, and as a result, the reusability of the policy-making work with a scientific underpinning.

The *EMO Feasibility Study* acknowledges the importance of open data. The “EMO should also take advantage of open data where possible. Open data is data that can be freely used, re-used and redistributed by anyone. [...] Using some form of open source software where relevant would allow an EMO to access a continuous peer-review of data ingestion, processing, corrections and indicator creation by statisticians, data scientists and academics.”³²

As stated in this final report, the 2019 Open Data Directive further extended the availability of re-usable public sector information (PSI) with *open science data*. . In both PSI, as open government data, and in open science data, there is a huge potential to fill in the data gaps without new data collection—the fact that data can be reused instead of being recollected is the main aim of the directive. However, open data does not mean *public data*. Open data means that taxpayer-funded research data can be repurposed, reprocessed, and reused—the Digital Music Observatory is an expert on such data science techniques.

The *Digital Music Observatory is not an alternative to the future European Music Observatory*, just its open source, open data driven voluntary, based on open collaboration with music industry stakeholders, music policy makers and users, academic researchers, individual and citizen scientists, and individual artists. Because we create fully automated research tools that are creating open datasets, and open source software, even our research infrastructure can be fully transferred to a future European Music Observatory³³.

We are not planning to make a competing data observatory. We want to provide a minimum viable model of creating at least a hundred useful indicators—selected from hundreds of indicator-candidates with user feedback—that goes through the unit-testing of data science and computer science, the peer-review of open-source scientific algorithm/software development, the methodological peer-review of science, and eventually user verification from music industry users. This will make sure that the indicators can be reproduced, refreshed, and placed in a future European Music Observatory with at least as good data quality as one would expect from a governmental statistical source or Eurostat.

The aim of the Digital Music Observatory is to maximize transparency by introducing to the policy context of Music Moves Europe, and the wider European music ecosystem the Open Policy Analysis framework. (See Open Collaboration, Open Policy Analysis, and Open Data.)

Open Collaboration, Open Policy Analysis, and Open Data

We aim to maximize transparency by introducing to the policy context of Music Moves Europe, and the wider European music ecosystem the Open Policy Analysis framework. (BITSS 2019; Hoces de la

²⁹Antal-Szentirmay: Launching Our Demo Music Observatory (blogpost)

³⁰Written evidence submitted by The state51 Music Group. Economics of music streaming review. Response to call for evidence (state51 Music Group 2020).

³¹The Open Policy Analysis Guidelines which grew out from several initiatives in research transparency, such as the Berkeley Initiative for Transparency in the Social Sciences, the Data Access and Research Transparency (DA-RT) group, the Center for Open Science and their TOP Guideline, the Meta-Research Innovation Center at Stanford University (BITSS 2019; Hoces de la Guardia, Grant, and Miguel 2020a).

³²In the EU, open data is governed by Directive (EU) 2019/1024 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (EUR-Lex 2019), which replaced the Public Sector Information Directive, also known as the ‘PSI Directive’ which dated from 2003 and was subsequently amended in 2013. Feasibility study for the establishment of a European Music Observatory (European Commission et al. 2020, p38).

³³In other words, our aim, fully in line with the intentions of the Commission expert who were encouraging us to make this proposal, and with the Feasibility Study, is to create open source scientific/statistical software and pilot open data that can be utilized in 4/4 identified data gaps related to music diversity and circulation in the European Music Observatory.

Guardia, Grant, and Miguel 2020b).

Our policy tools will make possible the first, large scale European application of the Open Policy Analysis, which grew out from several initiatives in research transparency, such as the Berkeley Initiative for Transparency in the Social Sciences, the Data Access and Research Transparency (DA-RT) group, the Center for Open Science and their TOP Guideline, the Meta-Research Innovation Center at Stanford University. Globally, the World Bank promotes this framework (Hoces de la Guardia, Grant, and Miguel 2020b; Berkeley Initiative for Transparency in the Social Sciences et al. 2020) and they are fully in line with the Open Science objectives of the European Union (Commission et al. 2020).

Figure 2: Our ambition to increase transparency with introducing the Open Policy Analysis into the European music policies and collaborative data use in the European industry.

We believe that existing data availability is better than that described in the *Feasibility study*. As stated in this final report, the 2019 Open Data Directive further extended the availability of re-usable public sector information (PSI) with open science data. In both PSI, as open government data, and in open science data, there is a huge potential to fill in the data gaps without new data collection—the fact that data can be reused instead of being recollected is the main aim of the directive. These open data sources are legally open but are not accessible without further investment, and our Consortium wants to make this investment, and produce about 50% of all the data needs of the future European Music Observatory.

It also mentioned the work CEEMID, a bottom-up initiative originally started by three collective management societies, and eventually joined by more than 60 stakeholders in 12 European countries to fill in some of these gaps with a) voluntary data integration among partners b) open data re-processing c) co-financed data collection. Our proposal wants to put the former CEEMID, currently named Digital Music Observatory, a more solid scientific and methodological foundation, to make it more user-friendly, and to exploit state-of-art statistical, data science and computer science methods to provide more comprehensive, timely, and accurate services for the European music sector.

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